

CONDENSATION OF DIPHENYL*iso*THIOHYDANTOIN WITH AROMATIC ALDEHYDES AND NITROSO COMPOUNDS

BY DEEPA PAL AHUJA AND SIKHIBHUSHAN DUTT

Diphenyl*iso*thiohydantoin, which is obtained by the action of monochloroacetic acid on thiocarbamide in presence of alcohol, contains a reactive methylene group, and as such easily undergoes condensation with aromatic aldehydes and nitroso compounds giving highly coloured condensation products.

The condensations are easily effected in presence of glacial acetic acid and acetic anhydride. The condensation products dye wool in bright shades from an acid bath.

Diphenyl*iso*thiohydantoin was first obtained by Lange (*Ber.*, 1879, 12, 595) by reacting monochloroacetic acid with *sym*-diphenylthiourea in presence of alcohol, and its structure (I) was subsequently ascertained.

It is isomeric with *sym*-diphenylthiohydantoin (II) obtained by Aschan and Zilliacus (*Ber.*, 1884, 17, 424) by altogether different methods. Both of them have a methylene group in the vicinity of a CO group, and as such it is expected that both the methylene groups should be reactive. But while it has not yet been possible to establish such reactivity in (II), in view of the highly reactive nature of the methylene group in (I), it has now been condensed with aromatic aldehydes and nitroso compounds yielding arylidene-diphenyl*iso*thiohydantoin (III) and aryliminodiphenyl*iso*thiohydantoin (IV) respectively.

Condensations are easily effected in presence of glacial acetic acid which really acts more like a solvent medium than a condensing agent. Only in a very few cases the use of a stronger condensing agent like acetic anhydride is called for. The condensation products with aromatic aldehydes are all bright yellow crystalline compounds and those with aromatic nitroso compounds, dark brown to black substances which dye

wool from an acid bath after precipitation from sulphuric acid in deep fast shades of yellow, brown, chocolate, mahogany and black.

Aromatic aldehydes and nitroso compounds (vide Tables I and II) have been condensed with diphenylisothiodantoin in this paper.

EXPERIMENTAL

Preparation of Diphenylisothiodantoin.—For the satisfactory preparation of this compound the following method was found useful after a number of trials: Thiocarbonyl (60 g.), monochloroacetic acid (27.4 g.) and rectified spirit (225 c.c.) were refluxed on the water-bath. The reaction was complete in about 2 hours, when from a clear fluid, the contents of the flask set to a crystalline mass. The product after cooling was left in contact with dilute hydrochloric acid for 1 hour, washed by decantation successively with dilute hydrochloric acid, water and cold alcohol, and finally crystallised from a comparatively large quantity of boiling alcohol in colorless, glistening prisms, m.p. 177°, yield 60 g.

The condensation of diphenylisothiodantoin with aromatic aldehydes took place with great ease in glacial acetic acid solution, by heating together molecular proportions of the two reactants in the solvent for about an hour. On cooling, the condensation product crystallised out in glistening crystals. Acetic anhydride was used in a few cases where the solubility of the condensation product in glacial acetic acid was found to be too high and therefore prevented separation of the condensation product. Glacial acetic acid, however, was used in the condensation of aromatic hydroxy aldehydes as acetic anhydride gave rise to acetylated products.

As regards the condensation of aromatic nitroso compounds with diphenylisothiodantoin, the condensations are best effected by heating the reactants together in glacial acetic acid medium without any condensing agent. Only the minimum quantity of the acid is used in order to facilitate the separation of the condensation product from the hot solvent on cooling.

TABLE I

Condensation of diphenylisothiodantoin with aromatic aldehydes.

No.	Condensation product with	M.p.	Colour in acetic acid.	Shade of dyeing on wool.	% Sulphur	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	Benzaldehyde	158°	Bright yellow	Lemon-yellow	8.94	8.98
2.	Furfural	100°	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	9.19	9.25
3.	Vanillin	226°	Deep yellow	Deep yellow	7.59	7.96
4.	<i>O</i> -Vanillin	263°	Do	Do	7.72	7.96
5.	<i>o</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	170°	Pale yellow	Pale yellow	8.13	8.00
6.	<i>p</i> -Nitrobenzaldehyde	176°	Bright yellow	Lemon-yellow	7.98	8.00
7.	Cinnamaldehyde	209°	Do	Bright yellow	8.12	8.13
8.	Hydrocinnamaldehyde	172°	Dark yellow	Pale brown	8.86	8.33
9.	Anisaldehyde	171°	Deep yellow	Light yellow	8.01	8.33
10.	β -Naphthaldehyde	164°	Light brown	Light brown	7.53	7.88
11.	β -Resorcyaldehyde	167°	Dark yellow	Chrome yellow	8.05	8.27
12.	<i>m</i> -Oxybenzaldehyde	163°	Do	Light yellow	8.37	8.60

TABLE II

Condensation of diphenylisothiohydantoin with nitroso compounds

No.	Condensation product with	M.p.	Colour in acetic acid.	Shade of dyeing on wool.	% Sulphur	
					Found.	Calc.
1.	<i>p</i> -Nitrosodimethylaniline	Above 280°	Dark brown	Black	7.72	7.96
2.	<i>N</i> -Nitrosodiphenylamine	"	Do	Dark brown	—	—
3.	<i>p</i> -Nitrosophenol	"	Do	Black	8.52	8.58
4.	α -Nitroso- β -naphthol	122°	Chocolate-brown	Chocolate	7.32	7.57
5.	Nitrosoantipyrine	148°	Orange-red	Dark mahogany	6.31	6.85
6.	Nitrosophenylhydroxylamine	—	Smoky brown	Black	—	—

DEPARTMENT OF CHEMISTRY,
UNIVERSITY OF DELHI.

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